

AN EFFICIENT SECURE DIFFERENT KEYWORD SEARCH IN ENCRYPTED CLOUD DATA

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Abstract:

The Sensitive privacy information, they are typically encrypted before uploaded to the cloud developing the FSM schemes over encrypted cloud data. First, we introduce the relevance scores upon keywords Second, support complicated logic search the mixed "AND", "OR" and "NOT" operations of keywords. Third, the classified sub-dictionaries technique to achieve better efficiency. Analyze the security of the proposed schemes in terms of confidentiality of documents, privacy protection of index and trapdoor, and un-link ability of trapdoor. Both the security analysis and experimental results demonstrate that the proposed schemes can achieve the same security level comparing to the existing ones and better performance in terms of functionality, query complexity and efficiency.

Key Words: Multi-Keyword, Fine-Grained, Cloud Computing & Logical Operations.

1. Introduction:

The cloud computing treats computing as a utility and leases out the computing and storage capacities to the public individuals. In such a framework, the individual can remotely store her data on the cloud server, namely data outsourcing, and then make the cloud data open for public access through the cloud server. This represents a more scalable, low-cost and stable way for public data access because of the scalability and high efficiency of cloud servers, and therefore is favorable to small enterprises. Note that the outsourced data may contain sensitive privacy information. It is often necessary to encrypt the private data before transmitting the data to the cloud servers. The data encryption, however, would significantly lower the usability of data due to the difficulty of searching over the encrypted data. Simply encrypting the data may still cause other security concerns. For instance, Google Search uses SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) to encrypt the connection between search user and Google server when private data, such as documents and emails, appear in the search results. The data owner needs to generate several keywords according to the outsourced data. These keywords are then encrypted and stored at the cloud server. When a search user needs to access the outsourced data, it can select some relevant keywords and send the cipher text of the selected keywords to the cloud server. The cloud server then uses the cipher text to match the outsourced encrypted keywords, and lastly returns the matching results to the search user.

Existing System:

Today's mail servers such as IMAP servers, file servers and other data storage servers typically must be fully trusted they have access to the data, and hence must be trusted not to reveal it without authorization which introduces undesirable security and privacy risks in applications. Previous work shows how to build encrypted file systems and secure mail servers, but typically one must sacrifice functionality to ensure security. The fundamental problem is that moving the computation to the data storage seems very difficult when the data is encrypted, and many computation problems over encrypted data previously had no practical solutions. The trivial solution of downloading all the data and decrypting locally is clearly impractical, due to the huge amount of bandwidth cost in cloud scale systems. Such ranked search system enables data users to find the most relevant information quickly, rather than burden some sorting through every match in the content collection Ranked search can also elegantly eliminate unnecessary network traffic by sending back only the most relevant data, which is highly desirable in the "pay-as-you use" Cloud paradigm. One of the most popular ways to do so is through keyword-based retrieval. Keyword-based retrieval is a typical data service and widely applied in plain text scenarios, in which users retrieve relevant files in a file set based on keywords. It turns out to be a difficult task in cipher-text scenario due to limited operations on encrypted data. Top-k multi keyword over encrypted cloud data. These schemes, however, suffer from two problems—Boolean representation and how to strike a balance between security and efficiency.

Limitations:

The authors of made attempts to solve the problem of top-k multi keyword over encrypted cloud data. These schemes, however, suffer from two problems Boolean representation and how to strike a balance between security and efficiency. In the former, files are ranked only by the number of retrieved keywords, which impairs search accuracy. Most of the existing proposals, however, fail to offer sufficient insights towards the

construction of full functioned searchable encryption as described above. As an effort towards the issue, in this paper, propose an efficient multi-keyword ranked search (EMRS) scheme over encrypted mobile cloud data through blind storage.

Overall Description:

Our main contributions can be summarized as follows: Introduce a relevance score in searchable encryption to achieve multi-keyword ranked search over the encrypted mobile cloud data. In addition to that, construct an efficient index to improve the search efficiency.

Software Description:

Client Application Development:

Client applications represent the most common application environment in use today. These are the applications that one would invoke by opening some type of form and initiating an action.

Execution Models / Compute:

One of the most basic things a cloud platform does is execute applications. Windows Azure provides four options for doing this: Virtual Machines, Cloud Services, Web Sites, and Mobile Services. Each of the Windows Azure execution models has its own role to play.

Virtual Machines:

To create a VM, you specify which VHD to use and the VM's size. You then pay for the time that the VM is running. Windows Azure Virtual Machines offers a gallery of stock VHDs. These include Microsoft-provided options, such as Windows Server 2008 R2, Windows Server 2012, and Windows Server 2008 R2 with SQL Server, along with Linux images provided by Microsoft partners. You're free to create VMs from your own VHDs and add them to the gallery as well. Wherever the image comes from, you can persistently store any changes made while a VM is running.

System Description:

System Architecture:

The data owner, the data user, and the cloud server. The data owner has a collection of data documents F to be outsourced to the cloud server in the encrypted form C. To enable the searching capability over C for effective data utilization, the data owner, before outsourcing, will first build an encrypted searchable index I from F, and then outsource both the index I and the encrypted document collection C to the cloud server. To search the document collection for t given keywords, an authorized user acquires a corresponding trapdoor T through search control mechanisms, for example, broadcast encryption. Upon receiving T from a data user, the cloud server is responsible to search the index I and return the corresponding set of encrypted documents. To improve the document retrieval accuracy, the search result should be ranked by the cloud server according to some ranking

Modules:

- ✓ System Setup and Blind Storage construction Module
- ✓ Data Secure Module
- ✓ Trapdoor Generation Module
- ✓ Secure Search Module
- ✓ Retrieve / Decrypt Module

Data Secure Module:

The data owner builds the secure data encrypted as follows: The data owner computes the d-dimension relevance vector $p = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_d\}$ for each document using the *TF-IDF* weighting technique. The data owner extends the p to a (dC2)-dimension vector P^* . For each document d_i , to compute the encrypted relevance vector, the data owner encrypts the associated extended relevance vector p using the secret key M_1 , M_2 and S . The each document is combine different blocks. The each block is a header, the header indicating that the blocks belongs to which document. Data owner select Enc() function and encrypt the document.

Trapdoor Generation Module:

To search over the outsourced encrypted data, the search user needs to compute the trapdoor including a keyword-related token *stag* and encrypted query vector Q as follows: The search user takes a Multi keyword from data owner and generates vector score, select two different keyword from received multi keyword after that encrypt the trapdoor and request to cloud for encrypted formatted. The search user sends Q , *stag* and a number k to the cloud server to request the most k relevant documents.

Secure Search Module:

Once receiving Q , *stag*, and k , the cloud server parses the *stag* to get a set of integers in the range of document. Then, the cloud server accesses index z in the blind storage and retrieve the blocks indexed. These blocks consist of the blocks and some dummy blocks. For each retrieved encrypted relevance vector P , compute the relevance score for the associated document d_i with the encrypted query vector Q . After sorting the relevance scores and send back of the top- k document that is most relevant to the searched keywords.

Retrieve / Decrypt Module:

The search user's attributes satisfy the access policy of the document, the search user can decrypt the descriptor using his secret attribute keys to get the document id and the associated symmetric key. The header id using for recovering the first blocks of the relevance data order and identify the blocks size.

Conclusion and Future Enhancement:

In this paper, I have investigated on the fine-grained multi-keyword search (FMS) issue over encrypted cloud data, and proposed two FMS schemes. The FMS_I includes both the relevance scores and the preference factors of keywords to enhance more precise search and better users' experience, respectively. The FMS_II achieves secure and efficient search with practical functionality, i.e., "AND", "OR" and "NO" operations of keywords. Furthermore, I have proposed the enhanced schemes supporting classified sub-dictionaries (FMSCS) to improve efficiency. For the future work, I intend to further extend the proposal to consider the extensibility of the file set and the multi-user cloud environments. Towards this direction, I have made some preliminary results on the extensibility and the multi-user cloud environments. Another interesting topic is to develop the highly scalable searchable encryption to enable efficient search on large practical databases.

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